

FRACTURE OF CIRCUMFERENTIALLY CRACKED FILAMENT WOUND GRP TUBES UNDER UNIFORM TENSILE LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Thin-walled hoop wound glass/polyester composite tubes with circumferential pre-cracks were tested under uniform axial tensile loading. Finite element methods were used to determine elastic deformation of tubes with different crack lengths. Membrane and bending stress intensity components were evaluated for tubes with different orthotropy ratios. Mode I fracture toughness parameters G_{IC} and K_{IC} were determined from the experimental and numerical compliance curves and the loads at crack extension. It was observed that the G_{IC} data obtained from the compliance calibration method show relatively large scatter. The mean values of G_{IC} were slightly dependent on the test method and were in the range 216.7 to 281.8 J m⁻².

INTRODUCTION

Fracture behaviour of composite materials under mode I loading conditions has received considerable attention recently. As a basic fracture mode, the mode I fracture of unidirectional composites with cracks propagating parallel to the fibres has usually been tested on flat specimens, either tensile coupons or bending beams. The double cantilever beam [1,2] is a commonly used geometry owing to its advantage in specimen preparation, testing and data analysis. In this paper, mode I fracture properties of unidirectional glass/polyester resin composite were studied using a hoop wound tube with a circumferential pre-crack under axial tensile loading as a new testing technique. The problem was investigated both experimentally and numerically. Due to the mathematical complexities it is very difficult to describe the fracture process of a filament wound tube with a circumferential crack in terms of stress intensity factors. In many cases the functional dependence of these factors upon tube geometry, crack length, applied load and stiffness coefficient can be established only through such numerical methods as FEM (finite element methods). Thin-walled tubes have been widely recognized as good geometries for measuring elastic and strength properties of various composites under simple or combined loading conditions. The geometry has also been used in recent years to study mode II fracture of unidirectional composites with cracks parallel to the fibres [3,4].

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Composite tubes were made by laboratory filament winding. The reinforcement was E-glass fibres of 13µm diameter and the matrix was an unsaturated polyester resin, Crystic 272. Specimens had an internal diameter of 50mm, gauge length of 110mm, nominal wall thickness of 1.0mm and winding angle of 89.5° with respect to the tube axis. The fibre volume fraction was 51 to 54% and the void volume fraction was less than 0.2%. Optimum fabrication was achieved, which produced a high quality composite with relatively small filament misorientation.

Pre-cracks of various lengths and 0.2mm width were introduced by laser cutting followed by tip sharpening with thin razor blades. The composite tubes were adhesively bonded to a pair of close fit and well aligned end grips which were then bolted to a servohydraulic torsion/tension testing machine.

A uniform axial tensile load was applied through the end grips at a constant displacement rate of 0.1, mm/min. All specimens were loaded until the onset of crack propagation.

The critical strain energy release rate for mode I fracture, G_{IC} , was determined using the compliance calibration technique.

$$G_{IC} = \frac{Pc^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{d(2a)} \quad (1)$$

where Pc is the load for crack extension, B is the tube wall thickness, a is the half crack length and C is the specimen compliance.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

The stress intensity factor K_I was evaluated using finite element analysis. The presence of a circumferential crack in a shell subjected to tensile loading creates two basic stress intensity components, G_m and G_b . The membrane stress intensity component G_m which opens the crack tip in tension is related to the tensile stress acting in-plane of the shell. The bending stress intensity component G_b is caused by the bending stress which varies linearly through the thickness of the shell, and opens the crack tip in bending. The general solution of the stress intensity factor K_I may be obtained approximately by superimposing the results of membrane and bending components in the following way

$$K_I/K_O = G_m + G_b \left(\frac{2y}{t} \right) \quad (2)$$

with

$$K_O = \sigma_m \sqrt{\pi a} \left((2b/\pi a) \tan(\pi a/2b) \right)^{1/2}$$

where σ_m is the membrane tensile stress, $2b$ is the tube circumference and t is the tube thickness with $y = +t/2$ on the outer surface and $-t/2$ on the inner surface.

A finite element package PAFEC was used to determine stress intensity factors in cylindrical shells with circumferential through cracks under uniform tensile loading. A finite element representation of one quarter of a tube was constructed [5,6]. The mesh consisting of 190 isoparametric 3-D elements with isotropic and orthotropic elastic properties is shown in Fig. 1. The analysis used 3-D quarter point crack tip elements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figs. 2a and 2b show the finite element results of membrane and bending stress intensity components G_m and G_b respectively. The results are plotted against the half angular crack length for three different orthotropy ratios $E = E_{11}/E_{22}$ and $R/t = 25$. The finite element data have been compared with the advanced shallow - shell theory results [5,6]. The numerical stress intensity factors were obtained for plane stress conditions which give the lower bound of the analytical values [5,6]. It is apparent that the factors are strongly dependent on the orthotropy ratio E and they generally increase with decreasing E . For the composite under consideration ($E = 3.7$), G_m increases from 1.0 to 1.17 for the half angular crack length from $\alpha = 5^\circ$ ($2a \sim 5\text{mm}$) to 20° ($2a \sim 17\text{mm}$). In the same range of crack lengths, G_b increases from 0.056 to a maximum of 0.1 followed by a decrease to 0.05 at $\alpha = 20^\circ$.

Comparing equation (2) with the more general form of the stress intensity factor

$$K_I = Y \sigma \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (3)$$

the geometric correction factor Y can be expressed as follows

$$Y = G_m + G_b \left(\frac{2y}{t} \right) \quad (4)$$

Since the G_b values are approximately one order of magnitude smaller than G_m , Y may be taken as

Fig. 1 Finite element model of one quarter of a cylinder [5].

Fig. 2a. Membrane stress intensity component G_m vs half angular crack length [6].

Fig. 2b Bending stress intensity component G_b [6]

$$Y \approx G_m$$

Furthermore, if G_m is assumed as the mean value over $\alpha = 0^\circ$ to 20° , equation (2) can be approximated by the following relationship

$$K_I = 1.13 \sigma_m \sqrt{\pi a} \quad (5)$$

with maximum error of 7.5%.

To compare the experimental and numerical elastic response of the composite tube with a circumferential crack extending from $\alpha=0^\circ$ to 52° , the experimental and calculated compliance curves are presented in Fig. 3. The agreement between the two approaches is fairly good, with a maximum difference of about 5% for short cracks and about 10% for long cracks. This implies that the finite element model properly modelled the elastic deformation of the composite tube. It also suggests that the crack tip stress conditions should be reasonably well described by the finite element stress intensity components G_m and G_b .

Fig. 4 shows the variation of the critical stresses obtained at the onset of crack propagation for different pre-crack lengths. The results exhibit an overall trend to decrease with increasing crack length. However, the relationship between the stress and the corresponding crack length does not seem to be a classical Griffith type. This may be due partly to the fact that the relatively low fracture stresses are very sensitive to any variations of such conditions as the local fibre volume fraction and crack tip geometry.

The critical strain energy release rate G_{Ic} was determined from equation (1) using the loads at crack extension and the numerical and experimental compliance curves. The results presented in Fig.5 show a relatively large scatter in G_{Ic} over the crack lengths considered. This is strongly related to the scatter in the fracture stress in Fig. 4.

Independently, K_{Ic} was evaluated from equation (5). The results of K_{Ic} and the corresponding G_{Ic} values calculated from $G_{Ic} = K_{Ic}^2/E_{eff}$ are presented in Fig. 6., where the effective modulus, $E_{eff} = 10.7$ GPa. The mean value and standard error for K_{Ic} was $K_{Ic} = 1.63 \pm 0.11$ MNm^{-3/2}. The extent of variation of G_{Ic} obtained using this method is similar to the G_{Ic} data shown in Fig. 5. The mean values of G_{Ic} and the standard errors obtained by applying the above techniques are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1
COMPARISON OF G_{Ic} VALUES

	G_{Ic} (Jm ⁻²)	
	Mean	Standard error
equation (1) with C_{exp}	216.7	30.0
equation (1) with C_{num}	281.8	69.5
equation (5)	270.5	36.8

Fig. 3 Experimental and numerical compliance curves

Fig. 4 Stress at crack extension as a function of crack length.

Fig. 5 The critical strain energy release rate G_{IC} from compliance calibration methods

Fig. 6 The critical stress intensity factor K_{IC} and the critical strain energy release rate G_{IC} calculated from equation (5).

CONCLUSIONS

1. The experimental compliance curve for a cracked composite tube showed good agreement with the numerical compliance obtained from finite element analysis.
2. The geometric correction factor Y was estimated numerically. The factor can be approximated by a constant value, $Y = 1.13$, with maximum error of $\pm 7.5\%$ for the crack lengths considered.
3. The critical strain energy release rate G_{IC} was calculated using both the compliance calibration method and the stress intensity approach. The mean values range from 216.7 to 281.8 J m⁻². The scatter is relatively large in all cases.

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